

HUMAN RIGHTS, THE HISTORY OF THEIR ORIGIN AND PRACTICES IN OUR COUNTRY

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ABSTRACT

This article talks about human rights and freedoms, their implementation by the state, the history of the development of the human rights problem and the process of formation of the currently existing international documents and the national legal structure, as well as reforms are being implemented in our country.

The study of human rights is one of the most urgent issues at the present time, when the process of forming a civil society and a humane legal democratic state is underway in my country. By the 21st century, the issue of human rights has become one of the most urgent problems of the international community. The reason why it has become an urgent problem is, firstly, the gross and systematic violation of human rights and freedoms by the states, and secondly, the issue of human rights often becomes a weapon of foreign policy of some states.

Human rights is a comprehensive concept that includes the aspirations of all humanity, the highest values, dreams and hopes of society. Human rights are the basis of current development and the demand of the time, and it is also one of the most important signs of a democratic legal state, which determines the level of democratic development of every country. It is known from history that there has never been a time when humanity did not fight for its rights, dignity, and decent way of living. During the struggle of humanity for its rights, ideas, opinions and many doctrines about human dignity, rights and freedoms are created, the main laws of the development of these theories and legal standards for strengthening human rights are created.

After the independence of our country, many laws and legislative norms of great importance were adopted in order to further deepen the reforms implemented in the way of democratization and liberalization of all spheres and aspects of our life, and to increase their effectiveness. Over the past period, hundreds of laws have been adopted that form the national legal system on human rights and freedoms.

First of all, human rights should be based on universal human values, universal civilization, experiences gained by other nations in this field, generally recognized principles and standards of international law. A democratic society based on human rights has internationally recognized principles, among them equality, freedom, fraternity, friendship between peoples

and nations, free expression of one's will, submission of the minority to the majority, equal rights of all citizens, election of the main government agencies, their reporting to the voters, the state and society rule of law and many other norms.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan also reflects the fact that all advanced values of our people, our nation, our statehood and the legal culture of humanity are closely related. Nowadays, states have strengthened the following important provisions on human rights in their Constitutions: Human rights and recognition and protection of freedoms are the obligations of the state; the catalog of human rights and freedoms conforms to international legal standards and the priority of international law in this field; human rights and freedoms belong to him from birth, that is, recognition of the idea and theory of natural law equality of human rights and freedoms to everyone; provision of guaranteed judicial protection of citizens; the need to ensure that the exercise of human rights and freedoms does not violate the rights of other persons [1].

The emergence of human rights is considered a long-term process and is directly related to the history of human development. Analyzing the issues of human rights, it is worth noting that at first they are the main sources of rights and freedoms formed on the basis of customary law, which arose from natural law. Human rights did not come into being only because of the need of a person to realize his abilities in the state, but they began to appear in the 4th-3rd millennium BC. The formation of the concept of human rights spans thousands of years, and at various times this problem is covered in religious, moral, or, if not, philosophical concepts, and visions of a system of norms that are equal for all people begin to appear. We must understand the times when the generation of human rights begins to be strengthened in the normative legal documents that certain rights of a person belong to him and that these rights must be ensured and observed, and the creation of legal mechanisms for their protection. Historical development processes of human rights issues, the base of international human rights documents existing at the present time, and the formation of national legislation have a great role.

By the 20 th century, the problem of human rights began to go beyond the jurisdiction of one state. In particular, the terrible consequences of the Second World War made the development of special international legal documents in the field of human rights protection and the creation of an international mechanism aimed at their protection the main task of the international community.

In our country, a specific legal system related to human rights has been established, and the basis of this legislation is primarily our Constitution. In our constitution, special sections and chapters have been allocated on human and civil rights and freedoms. opportunities for free development in the state, their constitutional rights and freedoms, rights, dignity, social protection, freedom to exercise their political rights, and their duties to the state and society are encouraged. Also, in Article 19 of our Constitution "All citizens have the same rights and freedoms and are equal before the law regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, belief, personal and social status" raised [2].

In the process of establishing a legal state and civil society in our country, a political and social environment is developing in which human interests are the main focus. In order to further

improve the mechanism of protection of human rights and freedoms in our country, by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 26, 2020 <<Human rights The National Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan >> was approved [3]. The implementation of the tasks defined in it ensures that human rights in our country are at the level of international demand. During the development of our country, a stable legal base was established that legally strengthened the entire complex of universally recognized human rights and freedoms, but also the types of state and public control in the field of human rights. procedures and mechanisms were created to determine and establish compliance with the protection of human rights and freedoms

Therefore, it is confirmed that the most important task of every state structure is to ensure the implementation of laws and other legal documents to ensure the observance of human rights.

References:

1. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan <https://lex.uz/docs/6451070> 01.05.2023, 03/23/837/0241.
2. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan <https://lex.uz/docs/6451070> 01.05.2023, 03/23/837/0241.
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on approval of the National Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. PF-6012 dated 22.06.2020 <https://lex.uz/docs/4872355> 21.04.2022, 06/22/113/0330)

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